

ECOLOGICAL AND BIOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF PATHOGENS OF WINTER HYBRID RYE MYCOSES IN THE FOREST-STEPPE OF UKRAINE

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Abstract

The article highlights the results of a study of the ecological and biological characteristics of pathogens of winter hybrid rye mycoses in the forest-steppe zone of Ukraine. It has been established that the dominant diseases are brown leaf and stem rust, leaf septoria, powdery mildew, and a complex of root rot. Snow mold, fusarium head blight, and smut are less widespread, but in years with high humidity, they can significantly reduce grain yield and quality. It has been shown that the development of pathogens is determined by a combination of their biological properties, varietal characteristics of hybrids, and climatic factors. The results obtained provide a scientific basis for improving the integrated crop protection system aimed at reducing the infection load and ensuring stable yield formation.

Keywords: winter rye hybrid, mycoses, rust, septoria, powdery mildew, root rot, fusarium, smut.

Introduction. In recent years, hybrid winter wheat has been gaining ground in Ukraine's crop structure thanks to its high winter hardiness, undemanding soil and climate requirements, and growing demand for grain for food, feed, and bioenergy purposes. Hybrid forms demonstrate a significant heterosis effect – increased yield, uniformity and quality of grain, as well as stability under various growing conditions. At the same time, the intensification of technologies, densification of crops, and shifting of sowing dates, combined

with climatic fluctuations in the forest-steppe zone of Ukraine, create conditions for an increase in the incidence of fungal diseases (mycoses) in crops [1, 2]. This necessitates a thorough study of the ecological and biological characteristics of mycosis pathogens in the context of hybrid rye, which may differ in plant phenology and response to the infectious background from varietal populations (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Phytocenosis of hybrid winter rye in the forest-steppe zone of Ukraine, 2025 (original photo)

Features of hybrid rye: higher stem density, modified leaf architecture, accelerated initial growth, and other phenodynamics that can modify the microclimate of crops (leaf surface moisture, wetting duration, aeration), which directly affects the intensity of primary and secondary infection by pathogens. At the same time, the

system of maintaining hybridity (using cytoplasmic male sterility or genetically determined fertility control) indirectly affects the structure of genetic resistance to diseases and the possible variability of plant responses to different pathogen pathotypes. In view of this, it is extremely important to generalize and deepen

knowledge about the biology of pathogens in specific ecological niches of the Forest-Steppe, their infectious potential, development cycles, overwintering and spread routes, as well as the factors that determine their harmfulness [3, 4, 5].

Thus, the relevance of this article is determined by the need for a comprehensive analysis of the ecological and biological characteristics of the pathogens of winter hybrid rye mycoses in the Forest-Steppe zone of Ukraine for the scientific justification of an integrated crop protection system, improvement of monitoring and forecasting of disease development, optimization of technological solutions, and minimization of losses in yield and grain quality.

The aim of the study is to identify the composition of dominant pathogens, describe their life cycles and critical periods of infection in the Forest-Steppe, establish the ecological determinants of disease intensity, and assess the role of biological and agrotechnical factors in the formation of the infectious background of hybrid crops.

Material and Methods. The aim of the research was to identify common diseases of winter rye and determine the species composition of their pathogens in the agrocenoses of the Forest-Steppe for further improvement of the comprehensive system of crop protection against pathogens.

In order to assess the impact of pathogens on the productivity of winter rye at the Levor Farm (Berdychevsky District, Zhytomyr Region), a long-term study was launched in 2024. It involves studying the characteristics of plant growth and development, adaptive properties, competitiveness, as well as the formation of yield and grain quality in modern varieties and hybrids of rye under organic and traditional production conditions.

Monitoring of the development of fungal disease pathogens was carried out at agricultural enterprises of various forms of ownership in the Zhytomyr, Kyiv, and Vinnytsia regions.

Disease monitoring in crops was carried out in accordance with generally accepted methods of phytopathological research [14], which included: systematic visual inspections of crops at key stages of organogenesis (sprouting, tillering, stem elongation, heading, grain filling); records on permanent plots (5×10 m) and selection of plant samples for further laboratory analysis; determination of disease development according to recording scales.

The climate of the Ukrainian forest-steppe is characterized by a temperate continental regime with mild but unstable winters, frequent thaws and periods without snow, sufficient but unevenly distributed moisture (especially in spring and summer), as well as significant fluctuations in temperature and precipitation. Such conditions significantly affect the epidemiology of key rye mycoses: prolonged exposure of plants to wet snow cover or overwintering with temperature changes promotes the development of snow mold (*Microdochium nivale*), while warm and humid springs intensify the development of powdery mildew (*Blumeria graminis* f. sp. *secalis*), rust diseases (*Puccinia* spp.), leaf spots (*Drechslera* spp., *Septoria/Stagonospora* spp.), while

wet periods during the flowering and filling phases create conditions for fusarium wilt (*Fusarium* spp.) with the associated risks of grain contamination with mycotoxins. The soils of the experimental plots are typical chernozems.

The results obtained were subjected to mathematical and statistical processing using methods of variance and correlation analysis. The reliability of differences was assessed using Student's criterion ($p \leq 0.05$).

Results. The most dangerous fungal diseases for winter rye include: rust (leaf and stem) as powerful defoliants and reducers of photosynthetic activity; powdery mildew as an early spring and spring-summer factor of assimilation surface suppression; leaf spots of various etiologies as a chronic factor of premature aging; snow mold as a critical risk of overwintering and thinning of crops; root and ear fusariosis as a cause of lodging, reduction in 1000-grain weight, and toxicological risks. For each group of pathogens, it is important to identify the optimum temperature and humidity, sources of inoculum (seeds, plant debris, soil, wild cereals), infection mechanisms (through stomata, mechanical damage, direct penetration), survival strategies (chlamydospores, sclerotia, urediniospores, etc.) and factors determining the dynamics of epiphytotics.

The situation is complicated by changes in the phytosanitary status of phytocenoses under the influence of climate change: the lengthening of the growing season, the increase in the frequency of warm and wet springs, and more frequent extreme weather events (from prolonged droughts to torrential rains) contribute to shifts in the phenology of pathogens, the emergence of new races and pathotypes, and changes in the proportion of individual diseases in the overall phytosanitary pressure.

Despite numerous studies of cereal mycoses, this issue has not been sufficiently studied for hybrid rye in the forest-steppe zone of Ukraine.

Based on a review of the literature and our field and laboratory (phytological examination of crop seeds) studies conducted in 2024–2025, it was established that hybrid winter rye is affected by a number of disease pathogens, the most dominant of which are fungi.

It should be noted that diseases whose pathogens affect rye plants in the early stages of development include root rot, in particular common fusarium, ophiobolus, and cercosporium; in early spring – snow mold and sclerotinia; in the period from germination to milk ripeness of the grain – powdery mildew, septoria; in the phenophase of tubing–milk-waxy ripeness of the grain – brown, stem, and yellow rust; during the flowering period–milky-waxy ripeness of grain – fusarium head blight, alternaria, helminthosporiosis, loose and smut, olive mold, black spot and basal bacteriosis [8].

Our research data show that the most common diseases in winter rye hybrid crops in the Forest-Steppe zone are brown leaf rust, leaf septoria, powdery mildew, and root rot. Snow mold, fusarium head blight, and smut have developed insignificantly in crop agrocenoses. One of the most harmful diseases of winter rye is brown leaf rust (*Puccinia recondite* Dietel & Holw.) (Fig. 2). Compared to other mycoses, its pathogen is

able to adapt to various external conditions and form aggressive races characterized by high resistance of spores to high temperatures and relative air humidity.

Figure 2. *Puccinia recondite* Dietel & Holw.

This disease appears earlier than others and quickly reaches an advanced stage. The pathogen's urediniomycelium is frost-resistant and can overwinter on winter crops and wild grasses that have been infected since autumn. Brown rust appears on the leaves and sheaths, initially in the form of reddish-brown pustules (uredopustules), and later as black pustules with a

glossy sheen (telopustules). They are usually located on the upper side of the leaves, less often on the lower side, and never merge into a solid spot, which distinguishes them from stem rust. Chlorotic and necrotic spots may form around the uredospores [6, 8, 9].

Linear or stem rust (*Puccinia graminis* Pers. f. sp. *secalis* Erikss. Et Henn.) is no less harmful (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. *Puccinia graminis* Pers. f. sp. *secalis* Erikss. Et Henn.

It affects leaves, sheaths, stems, awns, and spikelet scales, on which rusty-brown powdery pads initially form, merging into elongated lines of urediniopustules. At the end of the growing season, black convex telia appear in the places where uredinia form and next to them, which also merge into continuous lines. More than 300 physiological races have been identified in the stem rust pathogen.

The sources of infection are affected cereal residues (teliospores), affected crops of winter rye and other cultivated and wild cereals (urediogybnytsia in

living plant tissue). The harmfulness of the disease lies in the disruption of the water balance when the disease is severely developed. Yield losses can reach 60–70%. [8, 10]

Among leaf spots, the most common disease of hybrid winter rye is septoria, which can affect plants throughout the growing season, but causes the most damage during the stem elongation-ear emergence phase (*Septoria tritici* Desm.) or ear emergence-flowering phase (*Stagonospora nodorum* (Berk.) E. Castell. & Germano) (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. *Septoria tritici* Desm.

On leaves, the disease manifests itself in the form of irregularly shaped spots of various colors (light, light brown, yellow, brown) that grow and merge, causing the leaves to gradually lose their green color and dry out. Later, the affected parts become lighter in color, and small black pycnidia appear in the center of these spots. The nodes on the stem are affected, as are the scales on the green ear. It should be noted that the development of the disease intensifies when plants are injured, stressed, burned, etc. The harmfulness of septoria lies in the reduction of the assimilation surface of the leaves, their premature drying, early infection reduces

the number of grains in the ear, stem brittleness, underdevelopment of the ear, premature ripening of the grain, and a decrease in grain quality, which leads to crop losses of more than 40%. Intensive infection and development of the disease are facilitated by prolonged wet and warm windy weather, dense crops, excessive doses of nitrogen fertilizers, infected post-harvest residues, etc. [8, 11]

Annual crop losses are also observed from the infection of winter rye crops with powdery mildew (*Blumeria graminis* (DC.) f. sp. *Tritici* Speer.) [8] (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. *Blumeria graminis* (DC.) f. sp. *Tritici* Speer.

The disease develops intensively starting from the second half of May to early June. The pathogen affects leaves, leaf sheaths, and stems, and in years of severe disease development, it affects spikelets and awns. It manifests itself as a white cobweb-like coating. Gradually, the coating turns gray and brown. Sources of infection are plant debris, wild grasses, and winter crop seedlings.

During the epiphytotic development of powdery mildew, the entire leaf surface is affected, which dies prematurely, disrupting plant nutrition and, as a result, reducing plant productivity by up to 50%, which causes significant crop losses [12].

In the forest-steppe zone of Ukraine, winter hybrid rye is most often affected by common (*Bipolaris sorokiniana* (Sacc.) Shoemaker), fusarium (caused by fungi

of the genus *Fusarium* Link.), cercosporella (*Cercosporella herpotrichoides* Fron.) and ophiobolous (*Ophiobolus graminis* Sacc.) root rot (Fig. 6).

Figure 6. Root rot of winter hybrid rye

Common to all types of root rot pathogens is their connection to the soil, widespread distribution, ability to switch from saprophytic to parasitic nutrition, and lack of clear specialization in host plant infection [13].

Root rot develops throughout the growing season: in autumn during the sprouting-tillering phase, in spring after wintering during the tillering phase, flowering, or at the beginning of milk ripeness and when the grain ripens. It affects the root system, underground internodes, the base, and lower internodes of the stem. The main symptoms are browning and deformation of seedlings, the formation of brown stripes and spots on the leaves, the death of productive stems, white ears, empty ears, underdeveloped ears, and shriveled grains. In some years, in crop rotations with a high saturation of grain crops, grain losses from plant damage by root rot pathogens can exceed 30%.

It should be noted that, along with the most common diseases of winter rye in crop agrocenoses, there were others whose development did not exceed economic thresholds of harmfulness: snow mold, fusarium head blight, and smut.

The causative agent of snow mold is the fungus *Fusarium nivale* (Fr.) Ces. [8, 12]. The disease manifests itself in the spring, as soon as the snow melts, in the form of a cobweb-like gray or whitish coating with a pink tint. The disease is also known as winter rye blight, accompanied by partial or complete plant death. Crop damage by mold fungi occurs as a result of early snowfall on unfrozen soil, heavy snow cover, and temperatures close to zero under the snow, especially during late spring snowmelt.

It should be noted that worldwide, fusarium head blight is one of the most dangerous diseases of cereals. The causative agents of the disease are imperfect fungi of the genus *Fusarium* Link [8, 11]. The disease develops intensively under conditions of high humidity and low air temperatures in the second half of the growing season. At first, the ear acquires a pale pink hue, and then a coating of the same color forms on the scales, which gradually covers almost the entire surface of the ear. Fusarium head blight is easy to diagnose, since a healthy ear retains its green color, while an infected one

turns white. In wet and warm weather, small dark blue perithecia appear on the affected spikelets.

Along with crop losses caused by a decrease in field germination of seeds, a decrease in the number of grains in the ear, and a decrease in the weight of a thousand grains, fusarium can impair the baking or brewing qualities of the grain and also form dangerous mycotoxins in the harvested crop.

Ergot has also been found in rye crops. The causative agent of the disease is the sac fungus *Claviceps purpurea* Tub. [6, 8]. In infected flowers, the fungus mycelium grows, fills the ovary, and gradually turns into a black horn – a sclerotium ranging in size from 1 to 3 cm. Subsequently, fairly large purple sclerotia appear on the ear, forming instead of the grain and protruding beyond the spikelet scales. Ergot reduces the rye yield, and flour obtained from grain with an ergot content of more than 0.5% is unsuitable for baking bread and feeding livestock. The main source of infection of crops is sclerotia that overwinter in the soil and are contained in the seed material. Wild cereals contribute to the spread of ergot.

Thus, fungal diseases are dominant in hybrid winter rye agrocenoses. Their intensive development is due to the biological characteristics of the pathogens, varietal characteristics, and hydrothermal conditions of the surrounding natural environment during the vegetation period of plants. Therefore, to limit the development and harmfulness of pathogens, it is necessary to research and improve effective elements of a comprehensive crop protection system

Conclusion. As a result of field and laboratory studies conducted in the Forest-Steppe zone of Ukraine, it has been established that fungal diseases play a leading role in reducing productivity in winter rye hybrid agrocenoses. The most common among them are leaf and stem rust, septoria, powdery mildew, and a complex of root rot. These pathogens exhibit high ecological plasticity, are capable of forming numerous races, and adapt to changing hydrothermal conditions.

Snow mold, fusarium head blight, and ergot are less prevalent, but in years with high humidity and prolonged thaws, they can cause significant crop losses

and deterioration in quality. Contamination of grain with mycotoxins when crops are affected by fusarium is particularly dangerous.

The development and harmfulness of mycoses are determined by a combination of the biological properties of pathogens, the morpho-biological characteristics of rye hybrids, and the influence of hydrothermal factors. The identified patterns indicate the need to improve the integrated crop protection system based on a combination of breeding, genetic, agrotechnical, biological, and chemical measures, which will reduce the infection load, minimize the risks of epiphytotics, and ensure stable yield and grain quality.

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